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MESS 0051

MIMS 2.85.01 - Which POS are running the World into the Ground?
Comparing Conspiracy Facts & Theories

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ABSTRACT

This paper is merely a giant table comparing the top 12 hypotheses about “who to blame” with what is going on in this world, from the most common to the least common (literally only one person hypothesizing to the author, personally). Some of them are very commonly believed, and others are more rare hypotheses. Most of them are scientifically possible, some are purely pseudoscientific, and cannot be proved or disproved by any known means. The order of the listings left to right is, more or less, accurate to what seems like the biggest/most popular theories individuals in the altstream provide for the sources of crises. Getting a pass this time, or rolled up with the corporate oligarchs are “Big Tech,” “Big Pharma,” and “Big Data.” Also, the Police State is rolled up into the Deep State, as well. In other words, the loose definition President Trump relied on is refined to a very specific anti-“Constitutional Republic.” Most aspects of the Deep State are easily identified as *unelected*, meaning: **not democratic**.

Keywords: NWO - Deep State - Secret Societies - Illuminati - Aliens - Commies - Nazis

Big Chart of POS *Conspiracy* ^{Facts} _{Theories}

	NWO and minion orgs and socialism	Deep State/CIA and corps/MIC	Alien / Ancient Bloodlines	ETs or hyperdimen- sional attack	Spiritual Battle/Demons	CHUSSIA/ "Com mies"
Means (\$\$)	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Red	Light Pink	Bright Green
Access	Dark Green	Dark Green	Medium Green	Medium Green	Light Green	Dark Green
Motive	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Bright Green
Opportunity	Dark Green	Medium Green	Light Green	Light Pink	Dark Green	Dark Green
Evidence Q.	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Red	Light Green	Dark Green
Has announced themselves	Dark Green	Medium Green	Red	Dark Red	Medium Green	Dark Green
Empirical Data Strong	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Pink	Dark Red	Red	Dark Green
Tangible Assets	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Pink	Red	Dark Green
Ideology well understood	Medium Green	Dark Green	Light Pink	Dark Red	Dark Green	Dark Green
Historicity	Medium Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Red	Dark Green	Dark Green
War connection	Dark Green	Dark Green	Medium Green	Light Green	Bright Green	Dark Green
NGOs	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Pink	Light Pink	Dark Green
One World Government	Dark Green	Medium Green	Light Green	Red	Light Pink	Light Green
Clear Agenda	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Pink	Red	Dark Green	Dark Green
Published Materials	Dark Green	Dark Green	Red	Dark Red	Medium Green	Dark Green
Part of other coverups (chemtrails, Land grabs)	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Red	Light Green	Light Green
DNC/neocon	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Pink	Medium Green	Dark Green
Nationalism	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Pink	Dark Red	Dark Green	Light Green
Fed Reserve	Dark Green	Dark Green	Medium Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Pink

Reasoning

Key

Lowest evidence	Little to no evidence	Anti-thetical evidence	Little evidence to neutral	Some evidence to neutral	Mediocre evidence	"On the money" evidence	Increasing darkness = more evidence	Most evidence, most logic
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* Bear in mind the darkest green supersedes "on the money" and therefore includes it.

Select Observations

1. The most obvious one is that the human-based theories simply hold more plausibility, more evidence, and more likelihood.
 - a. While the New World Order evidence appears strongest overall, the communist takeover has a serious heft to it, as well; and it's likely the two are 'in cahoots.'
 - b. The Deep State, and Military Industrial complex, though, is fully embedded and has some of the most means, motive, and opportunity, and almost no mediocre evidence. **It is nearly fully evidenced.**
2. Ancient [alien/annunaki] Bloodlines did *about as well* as a Satanic agenda, and some will say this is good evidence that they **are** demons, or that they are involved in Satanic rituals. Firstly, we know the secret societies of the NWO are involved in Satanic rituals and the Human Flesh Industry. However, we don't get much farther than that, because of a lack of empirical "insider" data.
 - a. Maybe someone attained this data, but they were "offed"¹ because of related other coverups, namely:
 - i. Pedogate/pizzagate
 - ii. Chemtrails/geoengineering
 - iii. Panama papers, Burisma, etc., ie - money trails
 - b. Maybe the data is before our eyes, but we aren't able to see it due to some form of Quantum Mechanics based technological magick; ie - "code control"
3. ETs and hyperdimensional aliens did the worst, but "isn't that what they'd want you to think?"
 - a. Hence: pseudoscientific hypothesis²: it can neither be proven nor disproven, which is problematic from scientific/EPEMC perspectives.
4. The Federal Reserve seems to be the lone chink in the armor for communist takeover, and this may indicate:
 - a. The general state for the New Cold War
 - b. The conditions underlying World War 3.0 → III

¹ It isn't only enemies and workers for the Clintons and DNC that get 'suicided' or 'Arkencided' - Clintonated - many have been killed who were at all close to publishing about Pedogate. And T. Sotomayor's documentary "Surviving the Synagogue" resulted in (within 8 hours) complete deplatforming, and he has never released it again, for fear of being attacked like A. Jones. The most infamous 'assisted suicide' is not Epstein... it is State Senator Nancy Schaefer [GBJ Probing Deaths of Former Lawmaker, Her Husband - ABC News](#) & [Is Child Protective Services Trafficking Children? – PJ Media](#)

² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/volunteer/standards>

- c. The secret takeover of the Fed in an anti-mimsical “tug of war” with the banks in China they and the World Bank/IMF helped create (Frankenstein’s monster, so to speak).
5. The lack of empirical data for the Satanic theory is problematic, but again, could be merely a matter of “how you look at it.” For isn’t the drug problem, and the fact that some of our best visual evidence of demonic possessions seem related to drugs.
 - a. “The greatest trick the Devil ever played, was to convince the world he didn’t exist.”
6. The nature of the Deep State is not to announce themselves, but to work behind the scenes at controlling different parts of the American Empire and the world at large (via NATO). However, the NWO prefers to publish propaganda and ironical announcements of their power through art and media, particularly Hollyweird. But the greatest evidence lies with the “Operation: MOCKINGBIRD”³ factual data regarding the Deep State and Military Industrial Complex’s involvement in propagandizing the People.
7. Nationalism and “nation building” is one of the strongest chains of evidence, and the ETs have no incentive to encourage us to do it, from what can be logically deduced without mental gymnastics. This **may** support the idea that there are “friendly” aliens trying to protect us. It might not.
8. Seemingly out of nowhere, the Satanic agenda is the strongest of evidence, and also announced itself, long ago, “We are Legion.”⁴
9. The evidence quality strongest supports a communist agenda, from creating a Manchurian candidate - perhaps like Obama - to having the reigns of money control over the Clintons and especially the Bidens.
 - a. What’s interesting is how well these players “get along” (it seems) with the NWO “secret societies” and the Deep State’s Military Industrial Complex.
 - b. This may indicate a general agreement on how to “relieve” Americans of their liberties and rights, and divide and conquer the world.
 - c. Once bereft, Americans and other westerners have no choice but to submit to the new form of fascism, a sort of multi-headed “Hydra”⁵ or “Fourth Reich”
10. Is, therefore, a great weight of evidence existing for alternative theories to these front-runners?

³ See the Appendix A for links

⁴ “And he asked him, What is thy name? And he answered, saying, My name is Legion: for we are many.” Matthew 5:9 (KJV)

⁵ <https://marvelcinematicuniverse.fandom.com/wiki/HYDRA>

Table 2 - Alternative Alternate theories

	Nazi Takeover	Electric Changes to SSEC & PEC	The Jewish conspiracy	Muslim Brotherhood "society jihad"	Secret Space Program UFOs	"Fake Christian" takeover/SS's	LHC and CERN altering reality
Means (\$\$)	Light Green	Red	Dark Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green
Access	Dark Green	Light Pink	Dark Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green
Motive	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green
Opportunity	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Pink	Light Green
Evidence Q.	Light Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green	Light Green	Light Green
Has announced themselves	Red	Red	Light Pink	Dark Green	Red	Bright Green	Light Green
Empirical Data Strong	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green	Light Green
Tangible Assets	Light Green	Red	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green	Dark Green
Ideology well understood	Dark Green	Red	Light Green	Dark Green	Red	Light Pink	Light Pink
Historicity	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Green
War connection	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Red	Dark Green
NGOs	Dark Green	Red	Dark Green	Dark Green	Red	Light Green	Dark Green
One World Government	Dark Green	Red	Red	Dark Green	Light Pink	Light Pink	Bright Green
Clear Agenda	Dark Green	Red	Red	Dark Green	Red	Bright Green	Light Pink
Published Materials	Light Pink	Red	Light Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Light Pink	Dark Green
Part of other coverups (eg. pedogate, 9/11)	Light Pink	Red	Light Green	Dark Green	Dark Green	Light Green	Dark Green
DNC/neocon	Dark Green	Red	Light Green	Light Green	Light Green	Dark Green	Red
Nationalism	Dark Green	Red	Light Green	Light Pink	Dark Green	Dark Green	Red
Fed Reserve	Dark Green	Red	Dark Green	Red	Light Pink	Light Pink	Light Green

More Observations

1. While Evidence Quality and Empirical Data remain strong across all these alternative alternates, actually other than the Jihad motives, nothing is particularly strong. However, the evidence for fake Christians/Secret Societies remains better than for hyperdimensional ETs or a Satanic agenda. And this only makes sense. One has tangible evidence of **human** activity, which we can definitely observe, if given the opportunity; and the others are more loosely based upon metaphysical or even supernatural phenomenons.
 - a. The opportunities for them seem pretty weak, though.
 - b. These Christians were exposed, so they didn't really announce themselves, but we know they are there.
2. Meanwhile the other religions, of Jews and Muslims are interestingly not equal in opportunities. Of the two, the author expected a better showing of the Jewish conspiracy. But it seems to the author that there is just far more evidence of opportunities for the Muslim Brotherhood, based on published evidence, and actual results we see.
3. The lack of human aspects to the Solar System Electric Circuit and the changes to the Planetary Electric Circuit⁶, only underscore how antithetical the issue is vs. those who push the climate change lies and agenda - the NWO and puppets at the DNC/RNC and EU/UN. There's so much evidence against carbon mediate climate change, and so little for, it makes it hard to understand how these groups plan to use this for the NWO takeover. But they clearly do.
4. The LHC/CERN theory⁷ for the one world government is interesting, even unique, but while the EU and UN each want to be that One World Government, they don't really have the means to do it. NATO is where the real firepower lies. Davos is just a shitstain on the world stage, ultimately.
5. As for the Nazi takeover - a secret Hydra-like element - it was a lot of compelling aspects to it, as a hypothesis, but unlike the NWO, they haven't announced themselves.
 - a. **Unless the NWO are the Nazis themselves**, for which there is only minuscule - but compelling evidence... and it all goes through the CIA to the Deep State AND Military Industrial Complex
6. Please note the PEMC hypothesis of the electrical changes to the atmosphere and sun, etc. is not a conspiracy, except where humans have interacted with it or against the spread of the information about it, or in some cases, used it for war and propaganda related agendas.
 - a. Geoengineering [chemtrails]
 - b. Carbon related climate change lies
 - c. D.E.W.'s

⁶ Our Magnetic Universe

⁷ MESSr0002 - Welcome Neo

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Appendix A - Get Wrekt Conspiracy Fact Page of Operations

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⁸ At the exact moment I typed this, Perseus was catching Pegasus in the 1981 movie, "Clash of the Titans"

⁹ The existence of which this author can neither confirm, nor deny.

Appendix B - What You Can Do about the New Cold War & World War 3.0

Table 2 - Solution sets; Red is Attack, Green is Support, Blue is Neutralize

Individual Solutions	Family Solutions	Social Solutions	Political Solutions
<p>Read:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> "Hundred Year Marathon" <input type="checkbox"/> "Stealth War" <input type="checkbox"/> "Deceiving the Sky" <input type="checkbox"/> "Secret Empires" <input type="checkbox"/> "New Case for Gold" <input type="checkbox"/> "Atlas Shrugged" <input type="checkbox"/> "Grunch of Giants" <input type="checkbox"/> "How to Destroy America in Three Easy Steps" <input type="checkbox"/> "Unrestricted Warfare" <input type="checkbox"/> "Thick Face, Black Heart" <p>Train in firearms use Train in survival skills Train in Self-defense¹⁰ Play strategy games Use Signal, Telegram, Discord, etc. Promote digital security¹¹ Use cryptocurrencies¹²</p>	<p>Judeo-Christians: breed Educate kids about drugs properly¹³ Homeschool Co-ops Setup prep circles Use Farm CSAs Start spiritual study groups Promote modernized education Promote classical education of Greek, Roman, etc. history Teach kids about Republic histories Strengthen ties with family & extended family Lead church and school PTSA functions</p>	<p>Promote real cosmologies and history Strengthen ties with neighbors Setup Farmer's Markets Promote sustainable communities Promote STEM Discourage "snitching" especially regarding COVID/vaccines Attack pedophilia Attack industrial abortion Attack anti-patriotism Attack nationalism Attack institutions that are designed to attack churches and traditions and the right to bear arms Support pro-life and wholesome programs</p>	<p>Libertarians should join the Democrat Party Republicans should unify with independents Independents remove RINOs and neocons Support term limits Attack corruption on any level by anyone Collect and release digital evidence Form alliances Promote militias¹⁴ Attack the Police State Attack the Deep State Attack the NWO Support Property Rights Support the Bill of Rights Support real Liberalism</p>

¹⁰ <https://bit.ly/2Uh6ReL>

¹¹ [21st Century Cyber Security for the Common Person or Business](#)

¹²

https://www.academia.edu/47732738/Simple_Guide_for_Friends_Family_and_Common_Folk_of_how_to_get_into_Crypt

¹³ Preaching abstinence doesn't work; you need to be honest with kids about the different types of drugs and which ones God created (like Marijuana and Mushrooms) and which are man-made abominations (meth, bath salts, heroine, etc.)

¹⁴ [Central KY Airsoft](#)